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Self-Efficacy Perceptions of Secondary School Students regarding Speaking Skills

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Abstract

The current study aims to investigate the self-efficacy perceptions of secondary school students regarding speaking skills according to various variables. The study was designed in the survey model, one of the quantitative research methods. The study group consisted of 434 students, 212 females and 222 males, studying at the 5th, 6th, 7th and 8th grades of Bartın Borsası İstanbul Secondary School. The self-perceptions of secondary school students regarding speaking skills were examined according to gender, grade level, success in Turkish lessons, number of siblings, and educational status of parents. To this end, "Personal Information Form" and the "Speaking Self-Efficacy Scale" developed by Hasırcı Aksoy, Arıcı and Kan (2021) were employed for data collection. The data of the study was analyzed via SPSS 21.0. As the data was distributed normally, parametric tests were employed in the analyses. Independent groups t-test was applied for two variables and one-way analysis of variance was applied for more than two variables. According to the research findings, secondary school students have high level of self-efficacy perceptions towards speaking; there is no significance in these perceptions in terms of gender, grade level, number of siblings and mother's education level; yet there is a significance in terms of the success in the Turkish lesson and the educational status of the father. Accordingly, it was found that as the course achievement of the participants and the father's education level increased, self-efficacy perceptions towards speaking increased.

Keywords: Speaking, Self-Efficacy, Perception, Secondary School Students

1. Introduction

Language is one of the essential means in expressing ideas, feelings and desires in human life (Arfani & Sulistia, 2019). It fulfills this task through basic skills classified as comprehension and expression skills, and thus it becomes concrete rather than an abstract concept. Speaking, which is included in the expression dimension of basic language skills, is particularly an important skill that individuals apply in many areas of life, especially in daily communication, and stands out with its various advantages for both the speaker and the listener if it is used correctly and eloquently.

Speaking, which is acquired after listening in the language learning process (Güneş, 2014), is used by people to communicate with others in their daily lives. It is defined in multiple ways such as the activity of sending and receiving messages (Huebner, 1960 cited in. Iftakhar, 2012), the process of forming and transferring meaning via

verbal and nonverbal signs in different contexts (Chaney & Burk, 1998), a skill in which the need to communicate with the environment is fulfilled by transmitting messages through spoken language (Sihotan et al., 2021). According to Bahadorfar and Omidvar (2014), who point out that speaking is an important part of daily interaction, most of the time an individual's fluent and comprehensive speaking ability creates his/her first impression. Again, according to Miyauchi (2022), speaking skills give the first impression to others in real-life cases and are generally evaluated first by other individuals in the globalized world. It is crucial to form the eloquent speaking skills of individuals from early years, as it is the basis of quality communication and the first skill to be evaluated by other people. In this sense, the development of this skill is a prerequisite for success in many areas of life.

According to Güneş (2014), who emphasizes that speaking is not only an interactive process consisting of the transfer of feelings and thoughts, this skill is also an important area for developing learning, understanding, mental, emotional and social skills. Students comprehend a lot of knowledge by speaking, thus this process develops their speaking and cognitive skills. According to Öztahtalı and Şahin (2020), it is essential for students to realize the speaking problems they encounter during their education process and to have knowledge about their effective speaking skill levels, and to raise the consciousness of their speaking proficiency in order to ensure an academic achievement. One of the essential human abilities, speaking is also able to bring the mutual communication skill to the desired goal if it is used correctly and effectively. Considering all these views, it can be suggested that the way for students to be successful in their social and academic lives is to be successful speakers.

Although it is believed that acquiring the speaking ability in the mother tongue does not require an academic education at the first stage, the speaking skills of the students should be improved with the methods and techniques developed for how to use this skill in the most effective and correct way in the school environment, and it should be aimed to use the language effectively by the students (Kurudayıoğlu & Güngör, 2017). Since speaking is an extremely complex activity as a productive skill, factors such as grammatical accuracy, use of vocabulary, and clear pronunciation should be considered by students in classroom conversations (Sundari & Dasmo, 2014). At this point, teachers have the most significant duty and responsibility. In addition to being an example to students in effective speaking, teachers should also work to provide them with basic knowledge and skills. In the process of learning and teaching, teachers need to consider a number of factors that affect this process in terms of developing students' speaking abilities. Elements such as oral production, communication process, number of listeners, interaction patterns, amount of information processed, time interval, teacher, student and the conditions under which they interact are only a small part of improving speaking skills (Vilimec, 2006). In addition, pupils advance their formal speaking when teachers provide insights on managing their thoughts for presentation. They are able to speak better when they are chronologically and thematically able to manage their presentations in various methods. To this end, they need to practice managing their speech about troubles and resolutions, cause and effect, similarities and distinctions (Wallace et al., 2004). For this reason, in the process of transforming knowledge into skill, students should be given plenty of activities in the classroom environment and they should be enabled to gain experience in expressing themselves.

In order to allow students to get involved in classroom speaking activities, it is important to first make them willing to participate in these tasks. It is essential to support the theoretical knowledge to be transferred to the students and the appropriate physical environments to be provided with psychological elements. According to Güneş (2014), the psychological characteristics of the individual, emotions such as anger, fear and joy are reflected in the speech, and the tone of voice, speed and words used are also effective factors. In other words, the individual transfers his inner world to sounds and words during speech. This is also reflected in gestures and facial expressions. At this point, teachers need to make pupils want to have a speech, to encourage them and to make them feel confident (İşcan, 2015). According to Hamzadayı (2019), emotional dimensions along with cognitive and physical dimensions play a decisive role in a successful speaking process or in the origin of the troubles experienced in this process. One of the effective qualities that have an influence on the success of speaking is self-efficacy (SE).

The concept of SE (Sundari & Dasmo, 2014), which is accepted as a compatible predictor of students' motivation and learning techniques (Au & Bardakçı, 2020) and first introduced in Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory (Sundari & Dasmo, 2014), refers to individuals' belief in their ability to arrange and perform the actions required to produce specific acquisitions (Harris, 2022); individuals' sense of self-confidence about their success in a task (Jinks &

Morgan, 1999), beliefs about their abilities that will enable them to be successful in a job they are trying to perform (Linnenbrink & Pintrich, 2003). SE, which has recently evolved an critical variable in social and psychological research (Gekas, 1989), is considered as a strong determinant of one's efforts, strategies, further learning and work performance (Heslin & Klehe, 2006) and an important factor that needs to be taken into consideration in cases where pupils often lack confidence and motivation (Harris, 2022). In respect to this, it is vital to investigate and reveal students' SE perceptions.

Individual's self-beliefs about efficacy affect thought patterns that can improve or weaken performance (Bandura, 1992). Various studies on behavior change reveal a meaningful linking between SE perceptions and academic behavior (McCarthy et al., 1985), and show that students' SE beliefs are strong predictors of their academic achievement (Pajares et al., 2007). The perception of SE, which guides student participation through cognitive and behavioral ways (Kim & Shin, 2021), affects students' motivation, activity choice, and willingness to participate in a job (Sundari & Dasmu, 2014; Dixon et al., 2007), and forms the basis for psychological well-being and personal success (Pajares et al., 2007).

SE is a vital personal difference variable in education. It is believed that pupils with higher SE have less anxiety, behave more persistently when encountered with challenging assignments, are more motivated during in-class exercises and spend more effort on tasks (Mills, 2014; Zimmerman, 1999). According to Heslin and Klehe (2006), a higher level of SE directs individuals to work, fight in the face of difficulties and to be persistent. Deci and Ryan (1987) report that having a high SE perception will provide positive results for the individual and society in terms of physical and cognitive aspects such as creativity, flexibility, strong problem-solving skills, high self reliance and participation in activities. In addition, a higher sense of SE helps pupils to focus on learning tasks, perform better, and ultimately achieve success in learning goals (Au & Bardakçı, 2020).

Some theorists suggest that a low level of SE leads to motivation difficulties. If students think that they will not be successful in certain tasks, they will try completing them superficially, quickly give up and avoid or resist them (Margolis & McCabe, 2006). While a student with high SE believes that he can make a great effort when faced with difficulties, the one with low SE doubts his ability and sees everything he encounters as difficult and impossible (Sundari & Dasmu, 2014). According to Au and Bardakçı (2020), without sufficient SE, students may not engage in more difficult tasks and may not exhibit their skills. As a result, low SE perception hinders academic success and adversely affects psychology by creating self-fulfilling prophecy and learned helplessness in the long run (Margolis & McCabe, 2006).

There are various factors that affect individuals' low or high SE perceptions. According to Miyauchi (2022), SE basically consists of performance-based experiences, indirect experiences, verbal persuasion, and emotional states. Performance experiences, which refers to the sense of achievement as a result of successful experiences (Pajares & Valiante, 2006), are the most influential source in the construction of SE, as results interpreted as accomplished increase SE and those interpreted as failure decrease it (Oettingen, 1999; Pajares, 2003). Indirect experiences show the comparison between individuals' own abilities with that of their role models (Usher & Pajares, 2008). Students form their SE beliefs via the experience of indirect observation while others perform tasks (Britner & Pajares, 2006). According to Oettingen (1999), role models provide a standard for questioning one's abilities so that individuals can predict their SE by observing the successes and failures of others. Verbal persuasion is words of encouragement or feedback from parents or others who are considered important to one's performance (Usher & Pajares, 2008). As a result of verbal messages and social persuasions received from others, individuals' SE beliefs develop. While positive persuasion can contribute to encouraging and strengthening, negative persuasions can weaken one's self-belief (Pajares, 2003). Emotional states also show arousal through physiological responses while engaged in a particular task. Positive emotions can increase one's SE or reduce high anxiety levels for successful future performance (Britner & Pajares, 2006).

SE perceptions, which determine how people feel and think (Jones & Riazi, 2011) and constitute an important aspect of human motivation, directly affect certain actions (Alawiyah, 2018). However, as Schunk (1995) states, SE alone is not sufficient for affecting behavior. High SE will have no effect on performance without necessary knowledge and skills. At the same time, because of firstly conceptualization as a situation-specific belief (Sherer et al., 1982), SE is task-specific and becomes different from context to context. In this regard, SE should be

measured specifically, not in general (Raooft et al., 2012). One of the areas where SE can be measured specifically is speaking skill.

Conversational SE is the ability of an individual at work, school, family, on the phone, in a political meeting, etc. It is the belief of competence to effectively convey one's wishes, designs, feelings and thoughts in a situation (Hamzadayı, 2019). Speaking SE contains students' perceptions of their own skills to communicate in the target language (Shamiri & Farvardin, 2016) and is related to the psychological aspect of speaking. Speaking skill is analyzed under three dimensions, namely physical, cognitive/mental and affective. The factors such as emphasis and intonation, hand-arm movements, and eye contact are mostly related to the physical aspect, while the individual's ability to fully and properly express the message he wants to give to the other person is more related to the cognitive aspect. (Gölpınar et al., 2018). The affective dimension, on the other hand, is about how individuals feel during the action. The positive feeling in this sense enables the individual to find the power to use that action voluntarily and outside the learning environment (Topuzkanamış, 2022). In the affective dimension of speaking, there are affective reactions developed against speaking. The motivation and attitude of the individual to speaking, the level of anxiety before and during speaking, and the perception of SE for speaking skills forms the affective dimension of speech (Gölpınar et al., 2018). An effective speech is possible with the healthy functioning of mental and physical processes, as well as the emotional support of them. In this respect, students' perceptions of speaking skills, their willingness to speak, their motivation levels, and how they see themselves in speaking need to be emphasized and examined.

According to the literature on the perception of SE regarding speaking, studies abroad focus on foreign language speaking SE (Alawiyah, 2018; Darmawan et al., 2021; Sundari & Dasmo, 2014; Leeming, 2017; Liu, 2013; Quang et al., 2022; Rahayu & Jacobson, 2012; Shamiri & Farvardin, 2016). Studies in Turkey, on the other hand, are scale development studies to determine students' perceptions of speaking SE (Demir & Börekçi, 2022; Hasırcı Aksoy et al., 2021; Katrancı & Melanlıoğlu, 2013; Oğuz, 2016; Öztahatlı & Şahin, 2020; Sallabaş, 2013); pre-service teachers (Akın, 2016; Alan, 2021; Baki, 2018; Balbağ & Yenilmez, 2019; Çakır, 2015; Hayran, 2020; Katrancı, 2014; Oğuz, 2009; Oğuz, 2015; Özden, 2018; Özenci et al., 2021; Tekin et al., 2022; Tekşan & Çinpolat, 2018; Tunagür, 2021), undergraduate students (Demirel et al., 2020) and students who learn Turkish as a foreign language (Aydın et al., 2017; Kaplan Alptekin & Demir, 2022; Kurudayıoğlu & Güngör, 2017; Sallabaş, 2012) and secondary school students' speaking SE (Aydın & Kayman, 2021; Demir & Börekçi, 2021). Accordingly, research groups of these studies were mostly selected from pre-service teachers, and limited studies were conducted on students at the secondary school level. Literature review shows that studies in which secondary school students participated were limited to a single grade level. In this respect, it is believed that the research will contribute to the field in terms of being a study carried out with all classes at the secondary school level. Taking a stand from the problem statement of "Do the SE perceptions of secondary school students regarding speaking skills differ according to various variables?", the sub-problems of the research are determined as follows:

1. What is the level of secondary school students' SE perceptions regarding speaking skills?
2. Do secondary school students' SE perceptions regarding speaking skills differ according to gender?
3. Do secondary school students' SE perceptions regarding speaking skills differ according to grade level?
4. Do secondary school students' SE perceptions regarding speaking skills differ according to their success in Turkish lessons?
5. Do secondary school students' SE perceptions regarding speaking skills differ according to the number of siblings?
6. Do secondary school students' SE perceptions regarding speaking skills differ according to their mother's education level?
7. Do secondary school students' SE perceptions regarding speaking skills differ according to their father's education level?

2. Method

In this section, the research model, research group, data collection tool, data collection, and data analysis titles are given.

2.1. Research Model

This research, which aims to determine the SE perceptions of secondary school students regarding speaking skills in terms of various variables, was designed with a quantitative survey model. This model is defined as the quantitative or numerical description of trends, opinions, or attitudes in the universe with research carried out on a sample selected from a population (Creswell, 2014). The model is applied using questionnaires or interview protocols, a sample selected from the targeted population in line with the subjects of interest frequently. In addition to the changes that occur over time, the insight into a particular situation that took place at a specified time can also be explored (Christensen et al., 2020). The survey model is one of the leading methods used in the field of education due to its versatility, efficiency, and generalizability (McMillan & Schumacher, 2010).

2.2. Study Group

The study group of the research consisted of 434 students studying at Borsa Istanbul Secondary School located in the central district of Bartın province. Demographic information for the participants in the study group is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic information

Variables	Criteria	N	%
Gender	Girl	212	48.84%
	Male	222	51.16%
Grade level	5	100	23.04%
	6	114	26.27%
	7	91	20.97%
	8	129	29.72%
Turkish lesson grade	3 or less	90	20.74%
	4	141	32.49%
	5	203	46.77%
Number of siblings	0	30	6.91%
	1	163	37.56%
	2	174	40.09%
	3 or higher	67	15.44%
Educational level of mother	Primary school	114	26.27%
	Secondary school	128	29.49%
	High school	127	29.26%
	University	65	14.98%
Educational level of father	Primary school	57	13.13%
	Secondary school	119	27.42%
	High school	148	34.10%
	University	110	25.35%

As presented in Table 1, the research group (n=434) consisted of 212 (48.84%) female students and 222 (51.16%) male students. 100 (23.04%) of these students were 5th grade students; 114 (26.27%) were 6th, 91 (20.97%) were 7th, and 129 (29.72%) were 8th grade students. While 90 of the participants (20.74%) had a grade point average of 3 or below in Turkish lesson in the previous year, 141 (32.49%) had 4 and 203 (46.77%) had 5. In the study, 30 (6.91%) participants had no siblings, 163 (37.56%) had 1, 174 (40.09%) had 2, and 67 (15.44%) had 3 or more siblings. In terms of the educational level of mother, 114 (26.27%) were primary school graduates, 128 (29.49%) were secondary school graduates, 127 (29.26%) were high school graduates and 65 (14.98%) were university graduates. As for the education level of father, 57 (13.13%) were primary school graduates, 119 (27.42%) were secondary school graduates, 148 (34.10%) were high school graduates and 110 (25.35%) were university graduates.

2.3. Data Collection Tool

The data was collected by means of a research form consisting of "Personal Information Form" prepared by the researcher to determine the demographic characteristics of the participants, and the "Speaking Self-efficacy Scale" developed by Hasırcı Aksoy et al. (2021) for secondary school students, consisting of 4 sub-dimensions and 24 items, to measure their SE perceptions regarding speaking. Information on the development process of the scale is presented below.

After the analysis of the 48-item pool, which was prepared by using the studies in the literature and the opinions of the teachers, by 8 experts, corrections were made in 4 items, and 3 items were extracted from the item pool. In order to determine the intelligibility of the items, a total of 36 students from the 5th, 6th, 7th and 8th grades were asked to read the items and they were asked to express what they understood from each item. After this process, 4 items that the students did not understand or had different meanings were corrected. In the last case, a 5-point Likert-type draft form consisting of 42 positive and 3 negative items was created.

The 45-item draft form was applied to 205 secondary school students for confirmatory factor analysis, and the Cronbach Alpha value was calculated as .929 as a result of the internal consistency analysis for the reliability of the scale. In the analysis conducted on the outputs obtained for the item analysis, it was extracted 4 items from the scale. When the problematic items were removed, Cronbach's Alpha value for the internal consistency of the scale increased to .945. In the next stage, the scale was applied to 610 secondary school students for exploratory factor analysis (EFA) with 41 items. According to the .939 value obtained as a result of the Kaiser–Meyer–Olkin (KMO) test performed to decide the suitability of the sample size for factor analysis, it was seen that the data set showed a "perfect fit" for factor analysis. As a result of Bartlett's test of sphericity applied to determine whether the correlations between the items in the data set are sufficient [$\chi^2=4960.366$; $df=351$, $p=.00$], the data was found suitable for exploratory factor analysis (EFA). According to the results of principal components analysis applied to the scale, four factors and 27 items included in these factors were obtained. The factor load values were between .405 and .692 for the items in the first factor (affective), between .428 and .638 for the items in the second factor (content), between .406 and .692 for the items in the third factor (non-linguistic) and between .611 and .657 for the items in the fourth factor (being affected). When the correlation values of the four factors were examined, it was determined that the relationship between the factors of the measurement tool was significant and moderate. As a result of the analysis made to confirm the 4-factor 27-item structure of the scale, which was determined according to the EFA results, 3 items were removed from the scale. In order to determine the reliability values of the scale, the Cronbach Alpha internal consistency coefficient was examined, and the resulting .815 value showed that the items of the scale were consistent within themselves and the degree of reflecting the SE perception expressed was "acceptable and at a good level". At the last stage, in order to determine the distinctiveness of the scale items, the difference between the mean scores of the lower and upper groups was examined, and the independent groups t-test was applied for this. According to the results obtained, it was revealed that the speech SE perception scale developed for secondary school students has distinctiveness. When the obtained data were examined, a Likert-type measurement tool consisting of 24 items and 4 factors was obtained. The scale was scored as "Strongly Disagree" (1), "Disagree" (2), "Undecided" (3), "Agree" (4) and "Totally Agree" (5). Accordingly, the lowest score that can be obtained from the scale is 24, and the highest score is 120. Since the scale is a 5-point Likert type, average scores between 1-1.80 correspond to very low level of perception; 1.81-2.60 low; 2.61-3.40 moderate; 3.41-4.20 high and 4.21-5.00 very high perception.

2.4. Data Collection

After the researcher decided on the data collection tool to be used in the research, one of the authors who developed the scale was contacted and first of all, approvals were received for the use of the scale. Then, the Ethics Committee process of the study was initiated, and the research permission was received at the meeting of Bartın University Social and Human Sciences Ethics Committee with protocol number 2022-SBB-0185, dated 12.05.2022 and numbered 8. Following the start of the 2022-2023 academic year, the Bartın Provincial Directorate of National Education, to which the Bartın Borsa İstanbul Secondary School is affiliated, was applied with the necessary documents and the permission process was initiated. With the letter of the Directorate dated 26.09.2022 and numbered E-64441482-604.01.01-58925843, "approval" was obtained for the research. The research data were collected between 3-14 October 2022 during appropriate lesson hours by the researcher, and on the basis of student/parent voluntariness. The study was conducted in a total of 16 branches, 4 from each grade level. One of

the 435 scale forms collected from the participants was not included in the study because it did not provide the necessary data, and data analysis was started with 434 forms.

2.5. Analysis of Data

The data was analyzed using the SPSS 21.0 Package Program. Secondary school students' SE perception levels for speaking skills were revealed by using descriptive statistics such as arithmetic mean and standard deviation. Before examining the SE perceptions of the participants according to various variables, normality tests were applied. Skewness and Kurtosis values were calculated and found to range from -1.50 to +1.50. It was decided to use parametric tests since it was seen that the data was distributed normally. The differences in the SE perceptions of secondary school students regarding speaking by gender were determined by using independent groups t-test from parametric tests. The differences in terms of grade level, Turkish lesson success, number of siblings, father's educational level, and mother's educational level were analyzed using one-way analysis of variance, which is another parametric test. Post-Hoc analyzes were also used to determine between which groups the significant difference occurred in the variables analyzed via ANOVA. Percentage and frequency values were taken into account in the analysis of the data obtained with the Personal Information Form.

3. Findings

The findings of the study are presented in this part of the study based on the sub-problems.

3.1. Findings Regarding the First Sub-Problem

Findings related to the first sub-problem "What is the level of SE perceptions of secondary school students regarding speaking skill?" are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: SE perception levels of secondary school students regarding speaking

Dimensions	N	$\bar{x}$	S
Affective	434	3,54	,78
Content	434	3,60	,86
Extralinguistic	434	3,72	,84
Interaction	434	3,57	,95
Total	434	3,61	,73

As presented in Table 2, the average score of the SE perception of the secondary school students regarding speaking is 3.54 in the "affective" dimension; 3.60 in the "content" dimension; 3.72 in the "extralinguistic" dimension; 3.57 in the "interaction" dimension and 3.61 in the whole scale. According to the whole scale and all its sub-dimensions, the SE perceptions of the participants regarding speaking skills were found at a "high" level.

3.2. Findings Regarding the Second Sub-Problem

The findings related to the second sub-problem "Do secondary school students' SE perceptions regarding speaking skills differ in terms of gender?" are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Gender variable independent groups t-test results

Dimension	Gender	N	$\bar{x}$	S	sd	t	p
Affective	Female	212	3,49	,76	432	-1,203	,230
	Male	222	3,58	,79			
Content	Female	212	3,64	,87	432	,836	,404
	Male	222	3,57	,85			
Extralinguistic	Female	212	3,78	,86	432	1,435	,152
	Male	222	3,67	,82			
Being affected	Female	212	3,64	,93	432	1,493	,136
	Male	222	3,50	,97			

Total	Female	212	3,62	,73	432	,513	,608
	Male	222	3,59	,74			

According to Table 3, when the SE perceptions of the participants by gender are examined, no significant difference was found in the affective dimension ($p=.230>.05$), content dimension ($p=.404>.05$), extralinguistic dimension ($p=.152>.05$), being affected dimension ($p=.136>.05$) and the whole scale ($p=.608>.05$) since p values were found greater than .05.

3.3. Findings Regarding the Third Sub-Problem

Findings regarding the third sub-problem "Do secondary school students' SE perceptions regarding speaking skills differ according to grade level?" are given in Table 4.

Table 4: One-way analysis of variance results regarding grade level variable

Dimensions	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	sd	Mean Squares	F	p	Difference
Affective	Inter-groups	4,818	3	1,606	2,653	,048*	1-2
	In-groups	260,351	430	,605			1-3
	Total	265,169	433				1-4
Content	Inter-groups	3,055	3	1,018	1,362	,254	
	In-groups	321,407	430	,747			
	Total	324,461	433				
Extralinguistic	Inter-groups	2,925	3	,975	1,363	,254	
	In-groups	307,658	430	,715			
	Total	310,584	433				
Being affected	Inter-groups	2,381	3	,794	,866	,459	
	In-groups	394,349	430	,917			
	Total	396,730	433				
Total	Inter-groups	2,625	3	,875	1,610	,186	
	In-groups	233,645	430	,543			
	Total	236,269	433				

* $p < .05$

According to Table 4, when the SE perceptions of the participants regarding speaking are examined in terms of the grade level, there is no significance in the content dimension ($p=.254>.05$), extralinguistic dimension ($p=.254>.05$), being affected dimension ($p=.459>.05$) and the whole scale ($p=.186>.05$) since p values were found greater than .05. On the other hand, there is a significance in the affective dimension of the scale ($p=.048<.05$) since the p-value was found less than .05. As a result of the LSD test, which is one of the Post-Hoc tests applied to determine between which groups there is the significance, it was found that the difference was between the 5th grades and the 6th, 7th, 8th grades and in favor of the 5th grades.

3.4. Findings regarding the fourth sub-problem

Findings related to the fourth sub-problem "Do secondary school students' SE perceptions regarding speaking skills differ according to their success in Turkish lessons?" are given in Table 5.

Table 5: One-way analysis of variance results regarding success in Turkish lesson variable

Dimensions	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	sd	Mean Squares	F	p	Difference
Affective	Inter-groups	16,799	2	8,400	14,576	,000*	1-3
	In-groups	248,370	431	,576			2-3
	Total	265,169	433				
	Inter-groups	23,130	2	11,565	16,541	,000*	1-2

Content	In-groups	301,332	431	,699			1-3
	Total	324,461	433				2-3
Extralinguistic	Inter-groups	16,621	2	8,311			1-3
	In-groups	293,963	431	,682	12,185	,000*	2-3
	Total	310,584	433				
Being affected	Inter-groups	16,852	2	8,426			1-3
	In-groups	379,878	431	,881	9,560	,000*	2-3
	Total	396,730	433				
Total	Inter-groups	18,267	2	9,133			1-3
	In-groups	218,003	431	,506	18,057	,000*	2-3
	Total	236,269	433				

* $p < .05$

According to Table 5, when the SE perceptions of the participants regarding speaking according to their success in Turkish lessons are examined, there was found a significance in the affective dimension ($p = .000 < .05$), content dimension ($p = .000 < .05$), extralinguistic dimension ($p = .000 < .05$), being affected dimension ($p = .000 < .05$) and the whole scale ($p = .000 < .05$) since the p values were found less than .05. As a result of the LSD test, which is one of the Post-Hoc tests applied to determine between which groups there is the difference, the significance was found between those with a grade point average of 3 or below and those with an average of 5 in favor of the latter; between those with a grade point average of 4 and those with an average of 5 in favor of the latter. In addition, in the content dimension of the scale, a significance was found between those with a grade point average of 3 or below and those with an average of 4 in favor of the latter.

3.5. Findings Regarding the Fifth Sub-Problem

Findings regarding the fifth sub-problem "Do secondary school students' SE perceptions regarding speaking skills differ according to the number of siblings?" are presented in Table 6.

Table 6: One-way analysis of variance results regarding number of siblings variable

Dimensions	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	sd	Mean Squares	F	p
Affective	Inter-groups	1,235	3	,412		
	In-groups	263,935	430	,614	,671	,571
	Total	265,169	433			
Content	Inter-groups	,817	3	,272		
	In-groups	323,645	430	,753	,362	,781
	Total	324,461	433			
Extralinguistic	Inter-groups	,590	3	,197		
	In-groups	309,994	430	,721	,273	,845
	Total	310,584	433			
Being affected	Inter-groups	1,971	3	,657		
	In-groups	394,759	430	,918	,716	,543
	Total	396,730	433			
Total	Inter-groups	,674	3	,225		
	In-groups	235,595	430	,548	,410	,746
	Total	236,269	433			

According to Table 6, when the SE perceptions of the participants regarding speaking are investigated in terms of the number of siblings, no significance was found in the affective dimension ($p = .571 > .05$), content dimension ($p = .781 > .05$), extralinguistic dimension ($p = .845 > .05$), being affected dimension ($p = .543 > .05$) and the whole scale ($p = .746 > .05$), since p values were found greater than .05.

3.6. Findings Regarding the Sixth Sub-Problem

Findings regarding the sixth sub-problem "Do secondary school students' SE perceptions for speaking skills differ according to their mother's education level?" are presented in Table 7.

Table 7: One-way analysis of variance results regarding mother's educational status variable

Dimensions	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	sd	Mean Squares	F	p
Affective	Inter-groups	1,315	3	,412		
	In-groups	263,855	430	,614	,671	,444
	Total	265,169	433			
Content	Inter-groups	2,801	3	,272		
	In-groups	321,660	430	,753	,362	,164
	Total	324,461	433			
Extralinguistic	Inter-groups	4,925	3	,197		
	In-groups	305,658	430	,721	,273	,076
	Total	310,584	433			
Being affected	Inter-groups	1,971	3	,657		
	In-groups	394,759	430	,918	,716	,060
	Total	396,730	433			
Total	Inter-groups	,674	3	,225		
	In-groups	235,595	430	,548	,410	,065
	Total	236,269	433			

According to Table 7, when the SE perceptions of the participants regarding speaking are examined according to their mother's education level, no significant difference was found ($p=.444>.05$), in the content dimension ($p=.164>.05$), extralinguistic dimension ($p=.076>.05$), being affected dimension ($p=.060>.05$) and the whole scale ($p=.065>.05$), since p values were greater than .05.

3.7. Findings Regarding the Seventh Sub-Problem

Findings related to the seventh sub-problem "Do secondary school students' SE perceptions for speaking skills differ according to their father's education level?" are presented in Table 8.

Table 8: One-way analysis of variance results regarding father's educational status variable

Dimensions	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	sd	Mean Squares	F	p	Difference
Affective	Inter-groups	4,867	3	1,622			1-3
	In-groups	260,302	430	,605	2,680	,047*	1-4
	Total	265,169	433				2-3
Content	Inter-groups	8,579	3	2,860			2-3
	In-groups	315,883	430	,735	3,893	,009*	2-4
	Total	324,461	433				
Extralinguistic	Inter-groups	7,646	3	2,549			2-3
	In-groups	302,938	430	,705	3,618	,022*	2-4
	Total	310,584	433				
Being affected	Inter-groups	9,410	3	3,137			1-3
	In-groups	387,320	430	,901	3,482	,025*	2-3
	Total	396,730	433				
Total	Inter-groups	6,667	3	2,222			1-3
	In-groups	229,603	430	,534	4,162	,006*	1-4
	Total	236,269	433				2-3
							2-4

* $p<.05$

According to Table 8, when the SE perceptions of the participants regarding speaking according to their father's education level are examined, a significant difference was found in the affective dimension ($p=.047<.05$), content dimension ($p=.009<.05$), meta-linguistic dimension ($p=.022<.05$), being affected dimension ($p=.025<.05$), and the whole scale ($p=.006<.05$), since the p values were found less than .05. As a result of the LSD test, which is one of the Post-Hoc tests conducted to determine between which groups there is the difference, there was the significance between those whose fathers are primary school graduates and high school/university graduates, in favor of the latter in the "affective" dimension; between those whose fathers are secondary school graduates and high school/university graduates in the latter in the "content" and "extralinguistic" dimensions; between those whose fathers are primary school graduates and high school graduates in favor of the latter in the "being affected" dimension; between those whose fathers are secondary school graduates and high school graduates in favor of the latter in the whole scale.

4. Conclusion, Discussion and Recommendations

Speaking is a fundamental skill for communication. The correct and effective use of this skill depends on the healthy functioning of physical, cognitive, and affective processes. One of the factors that makes a person successful in the act of speaking is the perception of competence one has about himself as a speaker. In this study, the SE perceptions of secondary school students regarding speaking skills were investigated based on some variables, and the results were summarized and interpreted in this section.

This study revealed that SE perceptions of secondary school students regarding speaking skills were high. In the research done by Akin (2016) and Özden (2018) with Turkish teacher candidates, it was reported that the participants' level of SE perception regarding speaking was high. Alan (2021) reached a similar conclusion in his study with pre-service teachers. Katrancı (2014), who examined the SE perceptions of teachers candidates regarding speaking, found that the participants had a high level of SE perception. Kaplan Alptekin and Demir (2022) who investigated the SE perceptions of Syrian children under temporary protection in Turkey regarding speaking, revealed that the participants had a moderate SE perception. In another study (Aydın et al., 2017) conducted on Turkish learners, it was found that the SE perceptions of the participants regarding speaking were found moderate. It is believed that these results show the difference in SE perception levels of those who speak Turkish as a first language and those who speak Turkish as a foreign language. It is pleasing that secondary school students have positive feelings and thoughts about their speaking skills and consider themselves sufficient in this regard. The skill of students to express themselves is very crucial for students to be successful in other courses, especially in Turkish. Therefore, it is predicted that SE perception level regarding speaking will have an effect on academic success.

The variable of gender has no significance in terms of secondary school students' SE perceptions regarding speaking. This result is parallel with other research conducted on the SE perceptions of pre-service Turkish teachers (Akin, 2016; Baki, 2018; Özden, 2018), pre-service teachers (Alan, 2021; Balbağ & Yenilmez, 2019; Oğuz, 2015; Tekin et al., 2022); university students (Demirel et al., 2020) and those who learn Turkish as a foreign language (Aydın et al., 2017; Kaplan Alptekin & Demir, 2022; Kurudayıoğlu & Güngör, 2017; Sallabaş, 2012). Also, there are some studies that report a significance between SE perceptions of teachers candidates (Çakır, 2015; Gerez Taşgın, 2015; Hayran, 2020; Katrancı, 2014; Ocak & Erşen, 2015; Tekşan & Çinpolat, 2018; Tunagür, 2021; Türkmen Uslu, 2020) and 8th grade students regarding speaking/communication in favor of female students (Demir & Börekçi, 2021). It is believed that the characteristics of the participants in the research groups may have an effect on such different findings.

It was observed that the class level does not cause any significance in three and all of the four sub-dimensions of the scale in the SE perceptions of the participants regarding speaking. In the affective sub-dimension of the scale, there is a significance between the 5th grades and the other grades in favor of the former. In some other studies (Akin, 2016; Alan, 2021; Balbağ & Yenilmez, 2019; Gerez Taşgın, 2015; Katrancı, 2014; Oğuz, 2015; Tekin et al., 2022), the SE perceptions of teacher candidates regarding speaking increase as the grade level increases. It is estimated that the fact that pre-service teachers get more prepared for the profession as the grade level rises may have an effect on these results. Considering that the secondary school level does not prepare students for a

profession based on speaking/oral skills such as teaching and is one of the first steps of education life, this finding in the research is an expected result. Actually, in other studies examining the speaking anxiety of secondary school students (Arslan, 2018; Kavruk & Deniz, 2015), the results that the grade level variable does not affect decisively on anxiety also support this judgment. The findings of the studies (Kaplan Alptekin & Demir, 2022; Kurudayıoğlu & Güngör, 2017) can also be evaluated from the perspective that there is no significance in the SE perceptions of Turkish learners as a foreign language regarding speaking in terms of the age variable, taking into account the similarity of age level with class level. It can be said that the fact that the 5th graders have a higher SE perception in the affective dimension compared to the other grades may result from the fact that they have just passed from primary school to secondary school. Since students in primary school usually spend a long time with a single teacher and can express themselves more easily in lessons, they may have considered themselves sufficient in this dimension of speaking at the beginning of secondary school.

One of the variables that made a significance in the students' SE perceptions regarding speaking was the success in the Turkish lesson. It was revealed that there was a parallelism between the lesson points of the participants and their SE perceptions regarding speaking, and it was determined that the participants who were more successful in Turkish lessons had higher SE perceptions. This result shows similarity to the findings of the study (Demir & Börekçi, 2021), which determined that success in Turkish lesson is a determinant in the SE perceptions of 8th grade secondary school students regarding speaking. Studies conducted by Tunagür (2021) on Turkish teacher candidates; Balbağ and Yenilmez (2019) on the effect of GPA on the speaking SE perceptions of science and mathematics teacher candidates concluded that as the grade point averages increase, the level of speaking SE perception increases. One of the most vital conditions for being successful in the lessons is to actively participate in the lesson. It can be said that the students who actively participate in the lesson, ask and answer questions will be more successful in the exams. The student, who sees that the success of the lesson increases as he speaks, will be more confident in speaking and his SE will increase. There are studies showing that this situation is related to both speaking SE and other language skills. In the study of Demircan and Aydın (2019), which examined the SE perceptions of secondary school students regarding listening, it was reported that success in Turkish lesson created a significance in SE in favor of students who have a high-grade point. Gerez Taşgın's (2015) study in which pre-service Turkish teachers' listening SE was examined also revealed that GPA is a determinant of perceptions. In other studies examining 8th grade students' SE perceptions regarding writing (Demir, 2011) and reading (İnnalı & Aydın, 2014), it was reported that success in Turkish lesson is a determinant on the level of SE perception. Considering that other language skills as essential as speaking in academic achievement, that the findings support each other can be suggested. According to Jackson (2002), students' SE beliefs directly affect their exam scores and success in lessons.

This study reveals that there is no significance in their SE perceptions towards speaking in terms of the number of siblings of the secondary school students taking part in the research. In the study conducted by Demir and Börekçi (2021) on 8th grade secondary school students, it was revealed that in terms of the number of siblings there is no statistically significance on SE perception levels regarding verbal expression. In the research of Dzhazuzakov et al. (2020) conducted on university students; of Günönü Kurt (2019) on pre-service classroom teachers; of Uygun and Arıkan (2019) on social studies teacher candidates, there is no statistically significance in terms of communication skills average scores according to the number of siblings. This variable was also found to be effective in various studies on concepts such as academic SE (Satıcı, 2013), emotional SE (Akkuş Çutuk, 2019), general SE (Demircioğlu & Işık, 2020). However, there are also studies (Akalin & Adıgüzel, 2020) showing that the number of siblings is effective on anxiety, another psychological dimension of speaking. Although the high number of siblings means the intensity of the communication environment, it does not influence the SE perception of verbal expression. This is interpreted as an inadequacy in giving children a voice, showing interest, and positive interaction in the family environment (Demir & Börekçi, 2021).

The mothers' educational status of the participants was not determinative of their speaking SE perceptions. In the study of Tekin et al. (2022), which examined the SE perceptions of English teacher candidates regarding speaking, it was revealed that there was no significance in terms of the level of mother's education in the speaking SE of the participants. A similar finding was also detected in studies examining the communication skills of students, such as Türkmen Uslu's (2020) on pre-service special education teachers; Dzhazuzakov et al.'s (2020) on university students; Elkin et al.'s (2016) on health sciences students. In these studies, it was emphasized that the mother's

education level of the participants did not cause a significant difference in their communication skills. On the other hand, in the studies of Demir and Börekçi (2021) on 8th grade students, Akın (2016) on pre-service Turkish teachers, and Balbağ and Yenilmez (2019) on science and mathematics teacher candidates, the perception of SE regarding speaking was found to increase as the mother's education level increases. It can be understood that SE studies on other language skills also yield different findings. Studies conducted by Azizoğlu (2022) on secondary school students' SE perceptions regarding critical listening, Maden (2020) on pre-service teachers' SE perceptions regarding listening, and Ocağ and Karakuş (2019) on pre-service teachers' SE perceptions regarding digital literacy concluded that mother's education level does not cause any significance in the SE perception. According to Güllü's (2020) study, in which writing SE of 4th grade students, there was a significance between the students whose mothers were high school graduates and the students whose mothers were primary school graduates. In addition, there are also studies in the literature showing that mother's education level is not a determinant of the attitudes (İşcan et al., 2017) and anxiety (Kavruk & Deniz, 2015) dimensions of speaking.

Father's education level stands out as another variable that caused a significance in the SE perceptions of secondary school students regarding speaking. Accordingly, the students whose fathers are high school and university graduates have a higher level of SE perception than the students who are primary and secondary school graduates. In the study of Demir and Börekçi (2021), it was determined that the speaking SE perceptions of 8th grade students whose fathers are high school graduates differ significantly from those whose fathers are primary school graduates. The findings of studies that examined SE perceptions of Turkish teacher candidates (Akın, 2016) and science and mathematics teacher candidates (Balbağ & Yenilmez, 2019) regarding speaking are also parallel to these results. In Kayadibi's (2016) study, it was found that the speaking skills of the 7th grade students whose fathers are secondary school graduates and above were higher than others in Macedonia. It was found that the variable of father's education level caused a significant difference in other studies examining speaking anxiety (Arslan, 2018), listening (Maden, 2020), and reading SE perceptions (İnnalı & Aydın, 2014). In this study, it is estimated that the desire of fathers with a higher education level to spend more time with their children, especially in academic terms, may be effective in the fact that the mother's education level variable is not the determining factor in the students' SE perceptions, instead the father's educational status variable is the determinant.

Based on the results of the present study, suggestions for further studies can be listed as follows:

Activities that will increase the speaking SE perceptions of students with low Turkish grade point averages can be carried out.

Interviews can be conducted with students on the reasons why the father's educational status variable is a determinant of the SE perception regarding speaking.

Research can be conducted to address the relationships between the other affective dimensions of speaking skills, such as attitude and anxiety, and SE perception.

Due to the limited number of research on the SE perceptions of secondary school students regarding speaking, more emphasis can be placed on the studies to be carried out with students at this education level.

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